

water tank at 8 °C root temperature and 25 °C air temperature, 12 h photoperiod and kept there for 3 and 4 d, respectively. Net leaf photosynthetic rate and water use efficiency were measured using a steady state CO₂/H₂O porometer (Walz, Effeltrich, FRG) and a BINOS infrared gas analyzer (Heraeus, Hanau, FRG: provided by M. Dingkhun, IRRRI).

Chilling caused leaf yellowing, leaf wilting, and finally death of the seedlings. Net photosynthetic rate was 2.58 μmol/m² per s in the chilled but not chemically treated control and to 4.05 μmol/m² per s in plants sprayed with LAB173711 + tetcyclacis and kept at 8 °C for 3 d (see figure).

As chilling was prolonged, photosynthetic rate continued to decline to 2.86 μmol/m² per s in plants treated with

Water use efficiency (mmol CO₂/mol H₂O)

Changes in photosynthesis and water use efficiency of IR36 plants treated with LAB 17311 and LAB 17311 + tetcyclacis and kept at 8 °C for 3 and 4 d. Data are means ± S.E. of 5 measurements. IRRRI, 1990

LAB173711 + tetcyclacis and to 1.45 μmol/m² per s in the chilled but not chemically treated control. The water use efficiency was higher (10.7) in plants treated with LAB173711 + tetcyclacis than in control plants (5.5).

Use of abscisic acid analog LAB173711 alone was less efficient than combining it with tetcyclacis; that resulted in higher photosynthetic rate and water use efficiency. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Iron toxicity tolerance of rice cultivars in acid sulfate soils of Indonesia

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We screened 73 rice varieties and breeding lines for Fe toxicity tolerance in acid sulfate soils (Table 1) at Unit Tatas substation, Central Kalimantan, during 1987 wet season.

Seedlings were transplanted 21 d after seeding at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 1- × 3-m plots/variety. Fertilizer was urea at 90 kg N/ha and TSP at 60 and 0 kg P/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with two replications. Fe toxicity was scored 8 wk after transplanting.

Of the 73 entries, 18 were found tolerant of Fe toxicity (Table 2).

IR18349-53-1-3-1-3, IR19661-13-3-2, IR31917-31-3-2, IR9217-6-2-2-2-3, ITA212, and Pankaj did not respond to P fertilization. ■

Table 1. Some chemical characteristics of the acid sulfate soil at Unit Tatas substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Characteristic	0-20 cm deep	20-40 cm deep
pH (H ₂ O)	3.95	3.90
Total N (%)	0.41	0.19
Organic C (%)	2.78	1.70
Available P (ppm)	17.63	32.96
Exchangeable K (meq/100g)	0.19	0.13
SO ₄ ⁺ (%)	0.12	0.05
Al ₃ ⁺ (meq/100g)	14.19	15.70
Fe (meq/100g)	6.16	5.59
Na (meq/100g)	0.21	0.26
Particle size (%)		
Sand	0.22	0.21
Silt	33.41	31.14
Clay	66.37	68.65

Table 2. Fe toxicity tolerance and yield of rice on acid sulfate soils. Tatas, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Variety or line	Fe toxicity score ^a		Grain yield ^b (g/plot)	
	With P	Without P	With P	Without P
BR51-120-2	4	5	609	357
BW267-3	3	4	2166 a	1887 a
CR261-7039-236	4	5	1932 b	1653 bc
IR13146-45-2	4	5	1167	1068 e
IR18349-53-1-3-1-3	4	4	1143 de	1512 c
IR19657-87-3-3	4	6	1833 b	1275 d
IR19661-13-3-2	3	5	1311 cd	1764ab
IR21836-90-3	3	5	1179 de	1047 ef
IR31917-31-3-2	3	5	729 f	858 fg
IR6023-10-1-1	3	5	1878 b	1578 bc
IR9217-58-2-2	4	5	1104 e	804 g
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	4	5	1110 e	1479 c
ITA212	4	5	1443 c	1608 bc
ITA230	4	5	1317 cd	1194 de
Pankaj	4	5	1317 cd	1605 bc
Rohy15-WAR-3-3	4	5	1335 cd	1179 de
WAR52-384-3-2-2	4	4	1392 c	1107 de
Kapuas	3	4	2184 a	1650 bc

^a By the Standard evaluation System for rice. ^b In a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.